

Consumer phase identification in distribution grids using Graph Neural Networks based on synthetic and measured power profiles

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The Graph Neural Network identifies the phase labels with accuracy higher than 90%.
- Under noisy or unmetered demand, the Graph Neural Network achieves accuracy over 90%.
- Under various Photovoltaic cases, the Graph Neural Network yields accuracy over 90%.
- The Graph Neural Network yields accuracy of 92% in case of multi-phase connections.
- The grid losses and uncertain assets' parameters have minor impact on model accuracy.

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ABSTRACT

Most distribution system operators may not accurately record or completely maintain the phase connections for the numerous LV customers. Different consumer phase identification (CPI) approaches based on voltages, powers or other measurements are proposed in the literature. Due to the technical challenges in collecting voltage measurements, power measurement based approaches are preferable. Hence, this paper proposes a novel power based CPI methodology applying Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). The CPI methodology generates synthetic transformer power profiles assuming random combinations of phases for the measured load profiles, which are used altogether to train the GNN model. The GNN model is then tested using measured transformer and load power profiles. The performance of the methodology is evaluated in a test low voltage grid of 55 loads under various conditions of Photovoltaic penetration, Photovoltaics under maintenance, measurement errors, unmetered consumption, uncertain grid asset parameters and inaccurate phase connections. Further tests on a real low voltage grid with 111 loads prove the scalability of the methodology. The attained results show that the GNN model can achieve accuracy above 90% in most cases, outperforming various state-of-the-art methods.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and motivations

Electric power networks are usually precisely documented and monitored at the high voltage (HV) and medium voltage (MV) levels including sufficient automatization, control and geographic information systems (GIS) [1]. Low voltage (LV) distribution networks rarely have integrated solutions and monitoring is limited to the distributed automation at the transformer substation, and most recently, the smart metering infrastructure (SMI) [2]. In particular, distribution system

operators (DSOs) usually track the connectivity information for all customers at transmission and primary distribution networks [3]. Instead, the connectivity model, which specifies how the customers are connected downstream of the substation including their phase allocation information, may be inaccurate or unknown in LV distribution grids [4].

LV distribution grids, consisting of three-, two-, and single-phase lines, have a mixture of multi-, and single-phase loads or distributed energy resources (DERs), although in many countries, the residential customers are generally single-phase loads [1,5]. Since the actual phase

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Nomenclature**Abbreviations**

ADMS	Advanced Distribution Management System(s)
CPI	Consumer Phase Identification
DER(s)	Distributed Energy Resource(s)
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transformation
DSO(s)	Distribution System Operator(s)
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNN(s)	Graph Neural Network(s)
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GRA	Grey Relational Analysis
HV	High Voltage
LASSO	Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator
LV	Low Voltage
MIP	Mixed Integer Programming
MLR	Multivariate Linear Regression
ML	Machine Learning
MV	Medium Voltage
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PDF	Probability Density Function
PLC	Power Line Communication
PV(s)	Photovoltaic(s)
QP	Quadratic Programming
SA	Salient Analysis
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SF	Salient Frequency
SM(s)	Smart Meter(s)
SMI	Smart Meter Infrastructure

Sets

E	Set of edges
G	Set of graphs
K	Set of hidden layers
N	Set of neighboring nodes
O	Set of output layers
V	Set of nodes and input layers

Subscripts

neigh	Neighboring
self	Self
i	Index for numbering transformers

Superscripts

bus	Bus
k	Hidden layer
o	Output layer

Symbols

σ	Non-linear activation function
b	Optional bias
e	Edge embedding
h	Node embedding
v	Node
W	Weight
x	Input node feature
T	Transformer

connection of LV customers is unknown, incorrect, or inconsistent [6], DSOs often cannot accurately record or update lateral phasing information of the numerous LV customers [1,7]. Rather, this information is typically recorded manually by field personnel at the time of connecting to the grid. Besides, actual phase connections provided by GIS might not be up-to-date in various occasions, e.g., phase wiring misconfiguration, registration errors, grid reconfiguration, fault restoration, repairs or maintenance operations, load transfer, grid upgrades, potential cyberattacks, and new connections [7–9]. Furthermore, the phase connections for end-customers may have never been documented in the case of outdated networks, remote distribution transformers or bundled conductor systems [8]. Moreover, the phase connectivity cannot be determined using the SMI due to the current lack of relevant functions integrated in the smart meters (SMs) [10].

At present, the phase connectivity is usually determined and inserted manually into the GIS system; this poses significant challenges for the DSOs due to the large amount of end-user meters and complex line wiring [11]. Particularly, phase information is mainly validated through time-consuming, costly, and error-prone on-site inspection, which requires labor-intensive processes, significant manpower and material resources [12]. Apart from the manual intervention, alternative CPI approaches are available. Signal injection-based approaches are applied in small-scale electrical grids; yet, the need to repeat these approaches for all the LV connection points makes them inefficient and entails high capital and maintenance costs [7]. Hardware-based methods require high-precision phasor measurement units (PMUs) and communication between the consumer and the transformer. However, they are not common at the LV level due to the unavailability of Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems and the inevitable high costs in material, time, and manpower [13,14]. Moreover, the implementation of hardware-based techniques can cause momentary power disconnections, interrupting the continuous electrical supply and ultimately having both DSOs and customers suffer from monetary losses. Other methods involve the use of SMs in combination to Power Line Communication (PLC) lines, where the meter driven by a built-in function sends signals on the phases that are used by the receiver at the substation for phase matching [4]. Alternative approaches are based on SM voltage measurements which require a further device that identifies the phases by reading the phase shift between the phase reference at the substation and the phase of voltages at the SM [15]. Nevertheless, SM-based techniques require access to SM premises, manpower, high equipment cost and are also prone to human error. Furthermore, the SMI shall not be in normal operation and has to be PLC-based, albeit other communication protocols, such as General Packet Radio Service (GPRS), Wi-fi and ZigBee are also applied in practice [15–17].

The knowledge of phase connectivity is pivotal for the operation, monitoring, planning and maintenance of LV grids. Although the optimal operation of the grid requires multiple processes (e.g., power flow optimization, grid rebalancing, capacity planning of assets, power quality control, loss localization, state estimation, fault detection and reconfiguration/restoration analysis), their applicability at the LV level is often limited due to the unknown phase allocation [3,7]. The growing DER integration gives rise to further challenges for the DSOs that need to assess the hosting capacity of each connection; however, the respective calculations cannot be performed accurately due to the unknown phase connectivity [13,15]. It is evident that the knowledge of customer phase connectivity is indispensable part of various distribution grid management processes, and, therefore, the DSOs search for more cost-effective and less time-consuming approaches than the traditional techniques. This leads us to data-driven methods.

1.2. Literature review on data-driven methods

The massive roll-out of SMs turns the attention to data-driven CPI approaches that use data received by the established SMI and transformer substation. These data-driven methods can identify the

Table 1
Overview of existing power-based CPI approaches.

Ref.	Multi-phase loads/DERs	DER penetration	DER maintenance	No prior knowledge	Noise impact	Unmetered consumption	Parametric analysis	Uncertain grid parameters	Scalability analysis
[1]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
[2]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
[7]	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓
[8]	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓
[9]	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-
[12]	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	✓
[13]	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓
[17]	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
[18]	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓
[19]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-
[20]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-
[21]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	✓	-	-
[22]	✓	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-
[23]	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-
[24]	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
[25]	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-
[26]	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-
This paper	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

phase connectivity of LV end-customers by resorting to information about energy consumption, voltage, and current measurements, or even further data provided by the SMS and GIS platform. Data-driven CPI methods can be classified into three main categories according to the adopted measurements: (i) voltage-based [3,5,6,13,15,27–30], (ii) power-based [1,2,7–9,12,13,17–26], and (iii) hybrid when combining different data [11,14,31–33].

In terms of voltage-based methods, high precision time-synchronized voltage measurements are required. Since the individual devices may have clock deviations, the measurements may be asynchronously recorded [8,9,18]. Moreover, as large time intervals are used, it is challenging to define the similarity between customer and transformer profiles [8,18]. In addition, SMS are not intended for continuous synchronized voltage sampling at each individual LV customer, since they are used to monitor service quality at specific events [8,12,18,25]. The lack of sufficient historical voltage measurements usually emerges as the major challenge to applying voltage-based techniques [1,9]. Other hybrid methods require both voltage and power measurements [11,14,31,33], or both voltage and current measurements from each end-customer [32]. However, the acquisition of voltage time-series is usually not carried out on daily basis due to limited data storage. As a consequence, this study focuses on the utilization of power measurements, and hence, on the existing power-based approaches.

In terms of power-based methods, different approaches are reported in the literature utilizing the active power measurements. k-NN clustering and correlation methods can be applied between the transformer and the SM power profiles based on different correlation coefficients, such as Pearson and Kendall's rank [1,9]. In [1], the inclusion of a preprocessing stage for filtering the power profiles is proposed to significantly improve the accuracy of phase identification. The correlation analysis can be applied either on the whole time-series of power profiles, or on a subset of salient consumption variations known as salient or frequency analysis [9,12,13]. In [12], the authors first carry out a spectral analysis based on Discrete Fourier Transformation (DFT) to cut-off the low-frequency components of load profiles, and next, the features are extracted exclusively from the remaining high-frequency profiles that include the salient power variations. In [2,20], graph theory is used to generate trees by applying the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and utilizing the energy consumption measurements of SMS. In [23], the PCA-based approach is compared with the Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR) method. Authors in [26] apply first a MLR model, secondly a stepwise regression algorithm to identify the phases, and thirdly, a significance correction factor to update the results. Optimization-based problems are usually formulated applying

the principle of energy conservation for active and reactive power demand profiles on each phase [7,18,19,21]. In most cases, Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) or Quadratic Programming (QP) formulations are applied based on specific relaxations under noiseless or noisy conditions. Besides them, Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO)-based data-driven approaches are also reported with the main target to minimize the error between the summation of load profiles and the transformer profile [13,22]. Other techniques utilize the likelihood probability based on Bayesian inference [8], Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) considering geometric similarity [24], and Wavelet analysis for feature extraction [25]. Finally, [17] identifies the phase labels according to variance calculated by comparing the recorded with the predicted substation currents considering groups of SMS with mixture of phases.

The existing power-based CPI approaches are analyzed in Table 1 based on specific assessment criteria. Almost all existing methods require no prior knowledge of phase labels to ensure high performance. When scalability analysis is conducted [1,2,7,8,12,13,18,24], the proposed techniques does not suffer from accuracy degradation. The presence of both single- and multi-phase loads or DERs can also have an impact on the algorithm performance, and therefore, it is examined in several reports [1,2,18–22,26]. Besides them, noise level or measurement error according to the SM class is frequently considered in the evaluation of CPI techniques [7,8,13,18,22,23]. Unmetered consumption due to lack of metering device or electricity theft can also influence the model accuracy [9,12,13,17,18,23]. Furthermore, a limited number of studies carry out parametric analysis to optimize the model parameters of their respective methodology [18,21]. Apart from [18], the other power-based approaches overlook the impact of DER penetration on their methodology, while DERs under maintenance and uncertainty of grid parameters are not considered by the existing references. Overall, the literature review underlines that no power-based CPI method is available to ensure high performance considering all of the aforementioned criteria.

1.3. Approach and main contributions

To overcome the challenges underlined in Section 1.2, the paper goes one step further by presenting a new CPI methodology based on Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) leveraging the electrical grid model including topology and parameters of grid components, active power measurements from the end-customers and secondary distribution transformer. In the same manner as other ML-techniques, the GNN model also requires historical data for training. In this context,

Fig. 1. Proposed CPI methodology.

the synthetic transformer power profile data is generated by running multiple power flow simulations following the Monte Carlo approach. In particular, at each power flow simulation, a phase is randomly assigned to every measured power profile in the grid.

The proposed CPI methodology has been evaluated for all the drawbacks in the literature highlighted in Table 1. Moreover, even when the phase connectivity is known, the GNN model can be trained exclusively with synthetic data, hence, incorrect labels do not influence its performance. Additionally, as the method falls under the category of ML-techniques, it is expected that specific hyper-parameters shall be tuned optimally through a relevant parametric analysis. The GNN model robustness and scalability are also assessed for two LV grids of different sizes. For each grid, a separate GNN model needs to be trained utilizing relevant synthetic data, since the grids can have multiple variations in terms of topology, grid elements, loads, and generators. In particular, the sufficient number of Monte Carlo scenarios performed for each grid ensures the adequacy of the synthetic data, which is significant for the high accuracy of the GNN model. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there exists no power-based CPI approach that ensures robustness and high performance under the conditions mentioned above.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

1. a GNN based methodology is developed for identifying the phase connectivity in distribution grids. The methodology is able to effectively deal with various conditions of PV penetration, PVs under maintenance, measurement errors, unmetered consumption, uncertain grid asset parameters namely, transformer and line parameters and inaccurate phase connection;
2. the scalability and performance of the methodology are evaluated for various grid sizes and with a mixture of single- and multi-phase DERs and loads;
3. the performance of the methodology is compared with other CPI approaches (namely, k-NN and LASSO) subject to considerable measurement errors or unmetered consumption.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the individual stages of CPI methodology including synthetic data generation, GNN model training and application; Section 3 describes the inputs and the assumptions used for the simulations; Section 4 presents the simulation results of CPI methodology on a benchmark IEEE LV grid and a larger non synthetic European LV grid; Section 5 concludes the paper and paves the way for future work.

2. CPI methodology

The CPI methodology proposed in this work can be divided into three main stages, as displayed in Fig. 1. Firstly, the generation of synthetic data required for model training is carried out. Next, the GNN model is trained applying an edge classification approach. At the final step, the GNN model is tested with transformer power measurements and the identified load phase connections are compared with the known ones.

2.1. Graph neural networks

GNNs are a class of deep learning methods that capture the dependence of graphs through message passing between the nodes of graphs. In particular, they represent an extension of traditional neural networks to handle graph-structured data in a non-Euclidean structure form. Recently, GNNs have become a widely applied graph analysis method, especially in structural scenarios, where the data are naturally structured as a graph [34]. In this manner, the GNN architecture is defined directly on the structure of the analyzed system, which reflects the proper learning about system elements and their intricate inter-dependencies. The power distribution grids are also structured in a similar form with the graphs comprising nodes (buses) and edges (lines) that denote the connection between nodes. As a consequence, application of GNNs in power systems shows growing interest, with various classical paradigms in fault scenario, time-series prediction, power flow calculation, and data generation [35].

Generally speaking, a graph can be defined as $G = \{V, E\}$, where V corresponds to the set of nodes, and E represents the set of edges, particularly, the connections between the nodes. According to [36], three main graph learning tasks are found in the literature:

- Node-level tasks, which focus on nodes, include node classification, node regression and node clustering.
- Edge-level tasks, which classify edge types or predict an existing edge between two nodes, include edge classification and link prediction.
- Graph-level tasks, which focus on learning graph representations, include graph classification, graph regression and matching.

In this study, the main goal is to determine the connection of loads to the grid phases, i.e., the topology, hence the GNN edge prediction task is applied [37]. From the perspective of supervision, the training settings of graph learning tasks can be supervised for labeled data, unsupervised for unlabeled data, and semi-supervised for a small amount of labeled nodes. In our case, all nodes and edges have labels or values calculated based on the time-series data both in training and testing stages, therefore, supervised graph learning is applied.

2.2. Generation of synthetic training data

In the first step, the training data needed for the GNN model is generated starting from (i) active power time-series measurements from all SMs over a certain time horizon, and (ii) grid topology, in terms of electrical parameters for the distribution transformers and lines needed for the power flow calculations. In practice, most DSOs are aware of the grid parameters, since they carry out various relevant analyses, e.g., power flow and short-circuit calculations. Therefore, in this paper, perfect knowledge of the grid parameters is assumed. The set of synthetic data shall be adequate enough to ensure high performance, robustness, and adaptability under various grid conditions for the GNN model. Synthetic data are generated following a Monte Carlo approach,

Fig. 2. Conversion of distribution grid to a GNN graph.

where each scenario randomly assigns phases to all SMs supplied by a specific distribution transformer. For each Monte Carlo scenario, a three-phase power flow calculation is conducted to simulate the transformer time-series profile utilizing the measured active power profiles of the SMs. Any electric power system simulator capable of performing three-phase power flow analysis can be utilized. The number of Monte Carlo scenarios depends on the grid size and number of SMs. Ultimately, the stage of synthetic training data generation produces the (i) simulated power profile of the transformers and (ii) predefined random phases for SMs. These outputs are fed into the subsequent stage of GNN model training.

2.3. GNN model training

The training stage of the GNN model requires the outputs from the stage of generating synthetic data (namely simulated power profile of transformers and random SM phase connections) and the active power measurements from all SMs. The goal is to formulate the problem as an edge classification model, where a group of N graphs is generated based on the N Monte Carlo experiments, denoted as $G = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_N\}$. Each graph $G_i = (V, E)$ comprises nodes V and edges E , where each node has a set of input features, represented by $\{h_v : \forall v \in V\}$. Subsequently, as the training progresses, each feature of the nodes is processed by specific transformation functions. The resultant features of nodes and edges, post-transformation, are designated as node embeddings and edge embeddings, respectively. Similarly to other neural networks, a GNN consists of an input layer, some hidden layers—with their number being referred to as “depth”—and the output layer, wherein transformations occur and the final embeddings are generated as the output. The target of the model is to process graphs to generate edge embeddings that can be used for edge classification. The edges are classified into two classes, namely “1” and “0”; in particular, if an edge exists between nodes v_i and v_j , it has an embedding equal to “1”, otherwise “0”.

The topology of the distribution grid is systematically represented using graph theory, wherein the buses and lines of the grid correspond to the nodes and edges of the graph, respectively, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Each transformer within the grid is depicted as a set of three nodes in the graph, with each node signifying a distinct phase. Moreover, each SM in the grid, depicted as a node in the graph, is linked via an edge

Fig. 3. GNN model architecture adopted in this work.

to the appropriate phase node of the transformer. Fig. 2 illustrates an instance, where the connection of SM_n to phase C results in an edge between nodes $T_{i,C}$ and SM_n . Furthermore, each node in the graph possesses an active power profile of the respective SM as its node feature.

Regarding the transformation applied to the active power profile of each SM, an initial linear transformation is employed to project the node features onto a lower-dimensional space. Subsequently, as proposed in [38], the GraphSAGE algorithm is utilized to derive the embeddings of each node by incorporating information from both the node itself and neighboring nodes. The embeddings of node v within a hidden layer k , $\forall k \in K$, characterized by a set of node embeddings denoted as $\{h_v^k : \forall v \in V\}$, are computed by:

$$h_v^k = \sigma \left(W_{\text{self}}^k h_v^{k-1} + W_{\text{neigh}}^k h_{N(v)}^k + b^k \right) \quad (1)$$

$$h_{N(v)}^k = \sum_u h_u^{k-1}, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{N}(v) \quad (2)$$

where:

- σ is a non-linear activation function;
- W_{self}^k is a weight at layer k and “self” indicates the weight applied to node v ;
- W_{neigh}^k is a weight at layer k and “neigh” indicates the weight applied to neighboring nodes;
- $h_{N(v)}^k$ are the features from the neighboring nodes;
- b^k is optional bias.

From (1)–(2), it is clear that the embedding of each node in a neural network layer k is a combination of features of the node in layer $k - 1$ and the neighboring node features in layer k . This ability to derive insights from the neighboring nodes rather than solely depending on their own information is one of the distinguishing features of GNN. Once a certain depth K is reached, in other words, node embeddings up to certain layers of neural networks are computed, the edge embeddings are found in the output layer by:

$$e_{ij} = \left(h_{v_i}^k \right) \cdot \left(h_{v_j}^k \right) \quad (3)$$

where e_{ij} is an edge connected between v_i and v_j . The edge embedding is generated by the product of the embeddings of the individual nodes to which the edge is connected. The edge embedding is used to classify the existence of edges between two nodes. In this manner, it can be determined to which phase ($T_{i,A}$, $T_{i,B}$ or $T_{i,C}$) a single-phase SM is connected. Fig. 3 shows the GNN architecture of this work including the input data, as well as the input, hidden and output layers.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. LV Grids under examination: (a) IEEE LV European benchmark grid, and (b) non-synthetic European LV grid.

In an iteration – referred to as epoch –, the predictions of all possible edge embeddings are computed and next, the binary cross entropy loss with the ground truth data is calculated. As for the ground truth data, an edge embedding is equal to “1” if an edge between two nodes exists, otherwise, it is “0”. The calculated loss is then back-propagated and the weights W are corrected so that the predictions can approximate the ground truth data in the next epochs. The set of hyper-parameters to be predefined includes the training/validation ratio, learning rate, maximum limit of epochs and batch size. Further details on each hyper-parameter can be found in [38].

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Load Profile variation in terms of their average and peak powers for: (a) IEEE LV grid, and (b) non-synthetic European LV grid.

2.4. GNN model testing

At the testing stage of GNN model, the measured active power profiles from SMs and transformer(s) are used along with the trained GNN model (output of GNN model Training stage). The GNN model identifies the actual phases to which the SMs are connected. Particularly, the predictions of all edges are computed. For each SM node, the edge-embeddings to the three transformer nodes ($T_{i,A}$, $T_{i,B}$ or $T_{i,C}$) are calculated. Next, the embedding with the highest value determines the phase to which each SM node is connected. Additionally, the accuracy of the GNN model can be evaluated utilizing the predicted SM phase connections and the real i.e., known phase connections.

Table 2
Hyper-parameters.

Hyper-parameter	Value
Batch size	[1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32]
Learning rate	10^{-5}
Training/validation ratio	99%
Number of epochs	[0–1000]

3. Inputs and assumptions

This section describes the test grids and the active power profiles considered for the loads and PV systems.

3.1. Test grids

For this study, as a first grid, we use a benchmark IEEE LV European grid with three-phase distribution lines and 55 single-phase loads, each connected to a distinct phase [39]. As shown in Fig. 4(a), there is no sequential assignment of the loads to the three phases A, B and C. The second grid of large scale is a non-synthetic European distribution system with both primary and secondary distribution transformers of an urban area from the Mendeley database [40]. Our study focuses on the analysis of an individual secondary distribution transformer that supplies 111 single-, and three-phase loads through three-phase distribution lines, as illustrated in Fig. 4(b).

3.2. Load profiles

Two different datasets are utilized for the load profiles of the aforementioned grids.

The dataset for the IEEE LV European benchmark grid, consists of 55 daily active power profiles with a time resolution of one minute [39]. Hence, each time-series consists of 1440 data points, and each profile is assigned to each single-phase SM. Concerning the variability among the power profiles, Fig. 5(a) illustrates the peak power of each profile in function of the average power. As can be seen, the average power ranges from 0.1 kW to 0.8 kW, while the peak power varies from 1 kW to 15 kW. It is evident that the power profiles present diverse characteristics, indicating the heterogeneity of the dataset. This diversity is also useful for testing the robustness and performance of CPI methodology through the wide range of power profiles considered in the load flow calculations. Further analysis on the influence of heterogeneity on GNN model performance can be conducted in the future by selecting profiles with different degrees of power variation.

The dataset for the non-synthetic European LV Grid comes from the Irish CEER database, which includes 6436 active power profiles from various customers with a time resolution of 30 min for a period between 2009 and 2010 [41]. For this study, 111 random power profiles from the CEER database are selected and assigned to nodes with single- and three-phase loads. Moreover, the power profiles assigned to the three-phase loads are divided equally to the three phases. Similarly to the first dataset of the IEEE LV grid, time-series of 1440 data points extracted over 30 sequential days in the period 2009–2010 are assigned to the loads of the second exemplary grid.

3.3. PV profiles

Regarding the PV profiles considered for both test grids, random locations in the Swiss cities of Basel, Geneva, and Zurich are selected. Each end-customer of the grids can host up to one single-phase PV unit with an azimuth of 180 degrees, titling at 35 degrees and a combined system loss is assumed to be 10% of its instantaneous output. Since the examined grids do not include any PVs, the active power profiles for both summer and winter seasons are derived based on the web application Renewables.ninja [42]. A rated power of 10 kW is assumed

Fig. 6. GNN model accuracy and training time with respect to the number of experiments and different batch sizes for the IEEE LV grid.

Table 3

GNN model accuracy and training time with respect to the batch size for the IEEE LV grid.

Batch size	Test accuracy (%)	Training time (s)
1	98.2	4534
2	98.2	2219
4	98.2	2382
8	96.4	1380
16	98.2	813
32	92.7	690

for all profiles, and time-series of 1440 data points are considered. Although PVs of 10 kW are generally connected to three phases, the single-phase connection is assumed in order to examine the worst cases of single-phase PV integration. Furthermore, it is assumed that the PV meter reads exclusively the generated power without any aggregation with the household consumption. Both summer and winter profiles are assigned to the nodes with PV systems to take into account the variability of PV power production.

3.4. Hardware and software attributes

In terms of hardware, a processor Intel i7 CPU with 16 GB RAM and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 are used for all the stages of CPI methodology including synthetic training data generation, GNN model training, and testing. As for data preprocessing, the software tool Matlab 2024a is used [43], and the open-source simulator, OpenDSS 10.0.2 is utilized for the three-phase power flow simulations [44]. Synthetic training data generation is carried out with the Python version 3.12.0 [45], which allows interoperability with OpenDSS 10.0.2. The Python library torch geometric is used for the GNN model. Furthermore, version 3.11 of Python is used to run the GNN model, since the ML library (pytorch) is not compatible with Python 3.12 yet.

Regarding the hyper-parameters, different values are tested for the batch size, and number of epochs to be tuned optimally, as shown in Table 2. The final learning rate and training/validation ratio are also determined accordingly.

4. Results

In this section, the results from different analyses are presented and interpreted, followed by a discussion of the GNN model's limitations and future work.

4.1. Parametric analysis

First, an analysis is conducted for different batch sizes and number of Monte Carlo experiments. Fig. 6 and Table 3 underline that the highest accuracy of 98% can be achieved for batch size equal to 2 and at least 5000 experiments. Larger batch lead to a decrease in the number of graphs trained, hence would need a greater number

Fig. 7. GNN model accuracy with respect to the number of epochs for the IEEE LV grid.

Fig. 8. GNN model accuracy and training time with respect to the number of timesteps for the IEEE LV grid.

of experiments required to reach the aforementioned accuracy level. The main advantage of larger batch sizes is the reduction of training time at the expense of further Monte Carlo tests in order to achieve the same testing accuracy. The increase in batch size does not ensure improvement on test accuracy in spite of the training time reduction, as can be noticed in Table 3. Particularly, the batch sizes of 8 and 32 lead to lower accuracies (96.4% and 92.7%, respectively) than the batch sizes ranging from 1 to 4. However, there is no clear decreasing trend due to a high accuracy of 98% for batch size of 16.

In terms of the minimum epochs required to achieve the highest accuracy, various values are examined for the IEEE LV grid. As depicted in Fig. 7, the accuracy of 98% can be reached with 80 or 90 epochs, however, there are various short fluctuations with intermediate values. Since for 50 or more epochs, the accuracy shows a stable trend, this value is selected for the IEEE LV grid. In the case of the non-synthetic European LV grid owing to its bigger size, 300 epochs are chosen in the same manner.

The GNN model is not affected by the temporal resolution of time-series profiles, since the power value of each timestamp is considered as an individual point without any correlation with the time. Hence, the duration of each timestamp, e.g., 15 min or 30 min, does not have any impact on the GNN model performance. On the contrary, the number of timesteps can significantly influence the GNN model accuracy, as can be seen in Fig. 8. In the case of IEEE LV grid, it is evident that 1440 timesteps are required to achieve the accuracy of 98% regardless of the batch size. In addition, for batch size equal to 2, the 1440 timesteps can significantly reduce the training time compared to smaller numbers of timestamps. As aforementioned, larger batch sizes can lead to shorter training time, however, the improvement in training time is limited, as a higher number of timesteps is used.

By selecting the batch size of 2, 1440 timesteps, and 300 epochs, the GNN model accuracy is investigated for different Monte Carlo experiments in the case of the non-synthetic European LV grid. The main goal of this test is to define the required number of experiments with respect to the grid size for achieving an accuracy higher than 90%. As can be seen in Table 4, at least 12000 experiments are required

Table 4

GNN model accuracy and training time with respect to the number of experiments for the non-synthetic European LV grid.

Number of experiments	Test accuracy (%)
10 000	85
12 000	90

Fig. 9. Comparison of GNN model accuracies with aggregated and power-based load for the IEEE LV grid.

to reach the test accuracy of 90% for the non-synthetic grid of 111 loads. For the IEEE LV grid of 55 loads, 5000 experiments lead to an accuracy of around 98%. From both use cases, it can be estimated that the number of Monte Carlo experiments is proportional to the number of SMs multiplied with a factor ranging from 120 to 150.

It is evident that the Monte Carlo experiments do not have to be equal to the total possible phase combinations of the SMs. For the IEEE grid comprising 55 end-customers, a total of 3^{55} possible combinations exist. However, conducting 5000 experiments is sufficient to achieve an accuracy of 98%. As for the LV grid of 110 end-customers, although 3^{110} possible combinations exist, 12000 experiments lead to an accuracy of 90%. In addition, the experiments may have some recurrent combinations, since the phases at each grid node are selected randomly without considering the other experiments. Consequently, the GNN is capable of being adequately trained even with a smaller subset of the possible combinations. This advantage of GNN enhances its applicability in practical cases, where the number of end-customers increases considerably.

As a further test of this analysis, the impact of grid losses on the GNN model performance is examined for the IEEE LV grid. Therefore, the Monte Carlo experiments are conducted based on two different ways to express the power at the transformer LV terminals:

- aggregating the individual profiles measured by all SMs for the determination of transformer profile ignoring the grid losses;
- running power flows for the simulation of transformer profile (which considers the grid losses).

The GNN model is trained with different numbers of epochs in both cases and the accuracy is compared, as displayed in Fig. 9. It can be seen that for more than 17 epochs both approaches lead to an accuracy of 100%. As a consequence, the grid losses have a negligible impact on the GNN model performance and can be omitted. In this context, the load flow calculations are not required, simplifying the generation of synthetic training data and hence, significantly reducing the data preparation time. A similar analysis is going to be carried out including multi-phase loads in the future.

4.2. Measurement errors

In practice, SMs according to their class can cause measurement errors of up to $\pm 2\%$ because of noisy conditions [16]. In this study, a Gaussian noise percentage of 5% is injected to the load and transformer power profiles of the IEEE LV grid so as to assess the GNN model

Table 5

GNN model comparison with state-of-the-art methods in case of noisy measurements for the IEEE LV grid.

Method	Test accuracy (%)	
	No noise	With noise
GNN	100	95
LASSO	100	80
k-NN	82	68

Fig. 10. GNN model accuracy with respect to different levels of unmetered consumption.

performance in case of high noise levels. Next, the GNN model is trained with the noisy profiles, however, the noiseless profiles are used for model testing. The accuracy of the GNN model is compared with that of LASSO and the k-nearest neighbors (k-NN) algorithms, which are commonly used in the literature for phase identification problems. As can be noticed in Table 5, the LASSO algorithm has comparable performance with the GNN model under normal conditions without noise injection, while the k-NN algorithm achieves the lowest accuracy. However, the GNN model is more robust than the LASSO and k-NN algorithms under high noise levels. In particular, the GNN model maintains a high accuracy of about 95%, while the LASSO algorithm shows a considerable drop of about 20%, and the k-NN algorithm can yield up to 68%.

4.3. Unmetered consumption

In terms of the unmetered consumption, firstly, a percentage of 10% is assumed for the IEEE LV grid, therefore, 5 SM profiles are assumed to be unknown. As a result, the remaining 50 measured power profiles are considered for the Monte Carlo experiments in the stage of synthetic training data generation. At the GNN model testing stage, the measured transformer profile, includes the unmeasured SM profiles as well. However, the GNN model is used to identify explicitly the phases of the measured 50 single-phase SMs. When applying LASSO algorithm, the scenario of 10% unmetered consumption is repeated 100 times with random combination of unmetered loads, and next, the lowest accuracy of all tests is reported. As can be noticed in Fig. 10, the GNN model outperforms both the LASSO and k-NN algorithms, though the LASSO algorithm shows a considerable accuracy of 97%. Furthermore, the GNN model shows robust performance without any drop in accuracy when comparing the cases of fully-metered and 10% unmetered consumption. Next, the performance of the GNN model, LASSO, and k-NN algorithms is evaluated under increasing unmetered consumption levels. It is clear from Fig. 10 that the accuracy of GNN model drops gradually from 98% to 45% at 20% and 80% unmetered consumption, respectively. Nevertheless, the GNN model shows more stable performance than LASSO algorithm up to 40% unmetered consumption with slight decrease on the accuracy of about 5%. On the contrary, the LASSO algorithm shows a considerable reduction of more than 15% on the accuracy for growing unmetered consumption up to

Fig. 11. GNN model accuracy: (a) for different PV penetration levels (%) (b) based on a boxplot of quartiles for PVs under maintenance..

40%. Moreover, the LASSO algorithm shows a similar trend outperforming GNN model for unmetered consumption levels higher than 50%. The k-NN algorithm maintains an accuracy of 82% regardless of the unmetered consumption level. The reason behind this robust performance is that the k-NN algorithm identifies the unknown phase connections based on the correlation of each SM power profile with the transformer profile independently from the other SM measurements. From the evaluation, it is clear that the GNN model can outperform the state-of-the-art methods for unmetered consumption of up to 50%.

4.4. PV sensitivity analysis

At the first step of this analysis, three different PV penetration levels of 10%, 50%, and 100% are considered. For each PV penetration level, different shares of PVs are assumed under maintenance, when testing the GNN model. The PVs are considered to be disconnected, when they are under maintenance. Since the DSO is not always aware of the PVs that are under maintenance, they are considered during the GNN model training. Their power profiles are not reflected in the transformer profile in the GNN model testing stage, although they have been considered in the Monte Carlo experiments during GNN model training. Particularly, PVs under maintenance are not considered, when running the power flows for the calculation of the simulated transformer profile in the testing stage. All PV scenarios are simulated with the IEEE LV grid not only for training, but also for testing, since no actual measurements exist. Nevertheless, the random phase combination of PVs assumed for the simulation during testing is excluded from the Monte Carlo experiments considered for training in order to evaluate the GNN model properly. Particularly, the GNN model is not trained for the scenario that is assumed to represent the real case during testing. The shares of 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% are considered for the PVs under maintenance based on the main five quartiles. In Fig. 11, the box-plot for each PV penetration level is visualized based on the given quartiles of PVs under maintenance. Results show that the accuracy remains higher than 90% in all cases except for the scenario with PV integration level of 50% and 100% maintained units. In this case, a higher accuracy may be achieved if the GNN model is trained longer, however, this is avoided to keep a similar computational time for all test cases. As a result of this, the testing accuracy drops to 75%. Nevertheless, all the other cases of 50% penetration lead to accuracies

of 100%. As for the PV integration levels of 10% and 100%, it can be noticed that by increasing the share of PVs under maintenance, the accuracy decreases slightly up to about 92%. Overall, the GNN model shows robustness and high performance under growing PV integration levels, even when a high share of PVs considered during training are under maintenance during testing.

At the second step of this analysis, further loads and PVs are connected to the grid in addition to the loads in the base case of the IEEE LV grid. Particularly, the scenario includes the addition of not only single-phase, but also two- and three-phase loads and PVs. The idea is to examine if the presence of multi-phase loads and PVs can affect the GNN model performance. In the same manner to the first analysis, the random phase combination of multi-phase loads and PVs can only be simulated. Therefore, the SM and transformer profiles for testing are based on the load flow simulation, and not on real measurements. Furthermore, the random phase combinations of phase connections considered for the SMs and PVs of Monte Carlo experiments are excluded in the testing phase for the proper GNN model evaluation. Within this context, three random nodes are selected for the installation of:

- Single-phase units: Two loads and two PVs connected to the first node,
- Two-phase units: One load and two PVs connected to the second node, and
- Three-phase units: One load and two PVs connected to the third node.

For the generation of synthetic data used for GNN model training, 10 000 Monte Carlo experiments are carried out. In terms of testing, an accuracy of 91.80% is achieved showing that the presence of multi-phase units can affect the model performance. Nevertheless, the accuracy remains at high levels indicating the GNN model robustness under conditions with a mixture of multi-phase loads and PVs.

It is concluded that the GNN can detect with high accuracy the connection of single-, two-, and three-phase units. The GNN is trained based on the profile of each phase assumed in the Monte Carlo experiments, while the GNN result includes the assignment of each profile to a phase. Hence, for two- and three-phase units, the individual power profile of each phase will be assigned to the phase estimated by GNN. In this manner, the GNN estimates not only the phases of a multi-phase unit, but also the specific power profile of each phase of the multi-phase unit. In case that two single-phase end-customers with identical power profiles are connected to two phases of a grid node, the GNN can estimate the two phases precisely. However, the identification of the end-customer connected to each phase is not possible, since the time-series are identical and other customer attributes, e.g., identity number, are not used in the model. In practice, the connection of two- or three-phase units with identical power profiles per phase, e.g., PVs, electric vehicles and motors, is common, however, the connection of single-phase end-customers to different phases of a node and identical power profiles per phase is unusual. Besides that, the GNN is trained using power profiles of 1440 timesteps. Consequently, the power profiles of single-phase end-customers connected to different phases of a node are expected to have deviations which will enable the correct application of the GNN model.

4.5. Uncertain parameters of grid assets

As mentioned in Section 1, perfect knowledge of grid parameters is assumed for generating synthetic training data through multiple power flow simulations. Since tolerance might exist on the grid parameters, this section assesses how uncertainty in the values of line resistance and inductance can impact the GNN performance in the case of the IEEE LV grid.

Within this context, both resistance and inductance are assumed to be random variables having a uniform probability density function

Table 6

Excerpt of the matrix containing the 32 combinations of % deviations of resistance and inductance.

Combination ID	Resistance deviation (%)	Inductance deviation (%)
1	-6.39	6.21
2	8.39	-9.66
3	-2.88	-1.51
...
32	4.76	-7.69

Fig. 12. Impact of the uncertain line parameters on the GNN model performance in terms of number of misclassified load phases.

(PDF) of $[-10\%, +10\%]$ around the nominal values. As many as 32 different combinations of deviations (in %) of resistance and inductance are extracted from the joint PDF, by resorting to the low-discrepancy quasi-random Sobol's sequences to achieve effective space-filling properties at a small sample size [46,47]. Table 6 reports an excerpt of the resulting matrix.

The analysis of the GNN model performance subject to uncertainty in the line parameters is conducted on the IEEE LV grid. At each combination, the proposed methodology is first run by setting the values of resistance and inductance with the specified deviation for all the distribution grid lines. The predicted phases are then computed for every load and compared with the actual ones. The number of misclassifications is finally recorded and used as an indicator of the GNN model performance.

As shown in Fig. 12, in around 40% of the cases, the GNN model is able to correctly predict the phases of all the 55 loads. The highest number of misclassifications is 3, which is achieved only in one of the 32 cases. In particular, the negative variations of -7.1% and -9.1% at the line resistance and inductance, respectively, result in three misclassifications out of the 55 load phases. Besides that, combinations that cause high deviation of resistance and inductance lead to up to three inaccurate phase connections. The results indicate a low impact of uncertain grid parameters on the GNN model accuracy. From the engineering point of view, the resistances and inductances affect the grid losses that are accumulated in the transformer power profile. However, as concluded in Section 4.1, even by fully neglecting the grid losses—in other words, the resistances and inductances—the GNN model performance remains almost constant, being mainly driven by the load profiles.

In order to examine the influence of extreme uncertainties on the GNN performance, two further use cases are examined for the IEEE LV grid: (a) $\pm 10\%$ deviations on resistance (R) and inductance (X) of all lines, and (b) $\pm 20\%$ deviations on resistance and inductance of all lines and transformer impedance. Table 7 includes the results of the

Table 7

Number of misclassifications in case of extreme deviations on resistances and inductances of lines and transformer.

Deviations (%)				
Line		Transformer		Misclassifications
R	X	R	X	
+10	+10	0	0	1
-10	-10	0	0	1
+20	+20	+20	+20	1
-20	-20	-20	-20	2

Fig. 13. Accuracy of GNN model and state-of-the-art methods in case of incorrect known phase connections.

forementioned use cases. As can be noticed, the maximum number of misclassifications in the presence of extreme uncertainties when applying the GNN ranges from 1 to 2. Overall, the GNN model is robust against realistic or even extreme uncertainties in the parameters of grid assets.

4.6. Inaccurate phase connections

In practice, some phase connections may be known and can be taken for granted when generating the synthetic training data. However, if they are incorrect, they can have a negative impact on the GNN model performance. Within this context, a further sensitivity analysis is conducted based on different levels of inaccurate phase connections for the IEEE LV grid. While assuming that 20% of the phase labels are known, three levels of inaccurate phase labels are considered: (i) 0%, (ii) 20%, and (iii) 50%. The known phase labels are considered fixed during the Monte Carlo experiments, therefore, the random phases are assigned exclusively to the other unknown phase connections.

As can be remarked from Fig. 13, the GNN model accuracy decreases at 50%, when 20% or 50% wrong phase labels are considered. By comparing the GNN model performance with that of k-NN and LASSO algorithms, it emerges that both state-of-the-art algorithms surpass the GNN model. Particularly, the accuracies of LASSO and k-NN algorithms range from around 70% to 94% indicating that the known labels can deteriorate the GNN model performance when they are incorrect. Nevertheless, this limitation does not have an impact on the GNN model development, since the grid topology and power profiles are exclusively required, while known phase connections can be considered as redundant information. Due to the risk of deteriorating the GNN accuracy in case of inaccurate phase connections, it is suggested not to consider the known phase connections when carrying out the Monte Carlo experiments. As GNN can ensure high accuracies of almost 100% without the use of known phase connections, the GNN results can be used to verify the accuracy of known labels. As a consequence, the GNN can be used to detect wrong labels provided that they are not used during the training phase.

The wrong phase connections do not influence the k-NN algorithm accuracy, since the model is built by evaluating the correlation of each individual connection without any use of the known wrong labels. In

the case of the LASSO algorithm, the accuracy remains higher than the others, at values more than 90%, for all levels of incorrect phase connections. However, the results refer to a specific combination of known phase labels, while the performance of the LASSO algorithm may deteriorate when multiple random combinations of known connections are tested.

4.7. Discussion

In Section 4.5, the uncertainty of line resistance and inductance is represented with a typical uniform PDF, which assists on the generation of representative combinations. A similar approach could also be applied for the random combination of phase labels assumed for the Monte Carlo experiments. In this manner, the necessary number of Monte Carlo experiments could be significantly reduced by selecting only representative combinations of the investigation area. In terms of GNN model performance, this could also improve the accuracy when a high number of experiments is required due to the large grid size. As noticed in Section 4.1, the GNN model could reach up to 90% with 12000 experiments for the non-synthetic European LV grid of 111 loads. A PDF-based selection of representative combinations for the 12000 experiments may lead to higher GNN model accuracy.

As for the number of representative combinations selected for the uncertainty on the line resistance and inductance, the analysis is limited to 32 combinations sampled with quasi-random Sobol's sequences. Nevertheless, more accurate results about the stochastic distribution of misclassifications could be achieved by increasing the amount to the order of 1000 combinations. Another simplification regards the application of uniform deviations for the resistance and inductance to all lines in the context of each combination. Nevertheless, for a more comprehensive assessment, the analysis could also include the mixture of various deviations per combination. In particular, the lines are placed in different areas with varying weather and geospatial conditions, therefore, the deviations per combination can also vary. These factors shall also be considered when defining the group of deviations for each combination.

In Section 4.4, the impact of multi-phase loads and PVs on the GNN model accuracy is examined for a limited number of additional units. It is clear that the addition of different single-, two-, and three-phase loads and PVs at three nodes can lead to a reduction of the GNN model from 100% to about 92%. The drop of around 8% indicates that the GNN model performance is effected by the presence of multiple multi-phase units. Hence, it is of main importance to carry out a more in-depth sensitivity analysis for the second part including higher integration levels of multi-phase loads and PVs. In addition, a comparison of GNN with the state-of-the-art methods is to be conducted for both parts of the PV sensitivity analysis.

In terms of scalability, the GNN model is tested in two grids with 55 and 111 loads, however, the scalability shall be further examined. In particular, larger grids with more loads and nodes ranging from 500 to 1000 are required for a proper assessment of the scalability attribute. In this study, it is concluded that even for the grid of 111 loads the accuracy can reach 90% when 12000 Monte Carlo experiments are carried out. Since the number of tests would progressively increase for large-scale grids, first, an effective sampling approach, e.g., PDF, shall be applied to reduce the required number of Monte Carlo experiments.

In this study, emphasis is given on the evaluation of GNN utilizing the GraphSAGE algorithm. Its performance is compared to the state-of-the-art methods, LASSO and k-NN, which are reported in the literature for phase identification. Other types of GNN, e.g., Graph Convolutional Networks, Graph Attention Networks, and Graph Recurrent Networks, differ in the aggregation and propagation of information between nodes, influencing their performance. Given the superior accuracy of GraphSAGE in phase identification relative to the state-of-the-art methods, it would be interesting to investigate whether the aforementioned types of GNN can achieve similar performance

(e.g., number of misclassifications) in future research endeavors. Additionally, a comparative analysis of these GNN in terms of computational time and the required number of Monte Carlo experiments could also be conducted.

5. Conclusions and future work

In this paper, a CPI methodology based on GNN utilizing both synthetic and measured power profiles is proposed. From the analysis, it is concluded that 5000 and 12 000 Monte Carlo experiments can lead to accuracies of 98% and 90% for two low voltage grids of 55 and 111 loads, respectively. Moreover, the grid losses do not seem to affect the GNN model performance, when the aggregated load is used at the transformer profile without running the power flows.

Under noisy conditions, the GNN model maintains high accuracies of 95% surpassing the state-of-the-art methods of LASSO and k-NN. In the case of unmetered consumption, the GNN model can outperform both LASSO and k-NN algorithms for unmetered consumption levels up to 50%.

Under various Photovoltaic scenarios, the GNN model also presents a robust performance with accuracies higher than 90%. Particularly, the GNN model shows limited impact from Photovoltaics that are not considered during testing, since they are disconnected for maintenance purposes. Furthermore, the presence of mixed multi-phase loads and Photovoltaics does not seem to affect the GNN model performance significantly.

Considering the uncertainty of line resistance and inductance, various combinations of deviations are tested based on a uniform probability density function. It is evident that the GNN model maintains a high accuracy of about 95% with up to 3 wrong phase labels. As a consequence, the deviations in the values of resistance and inductance seem to have a negligible impact on the GNN model accuracy, similarly to the grid losses.

An important limitation found in this study is that the inaccurate phase labels shall not be considered in generating the synthetic training data, since they can deteriorate the GNN model performance. In the frame of future work, a proper sampling approach shall be incorporated for the definition of random phase combinations in order to limit the number of Monte Carlo experiments required. This will considerably assist the GNN model assessment at larger-scale grids. Finally, further scenarios for the installation of multiple multi-phase Photovoltaics and loads are to be examined in order to ensure the GNN model robustness to a higher extent.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chandra Sekhar Charan Dande: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Nikolaos A. Efkarpidis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Matthias Christen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mirko Ginocchi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Antonello Monti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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